

INTEGRATION OF GLOBAL CITIZENSHIP EDUCATION COMPETENCIES (GCED) IN THE TEACHING OF INTERMEDIATE ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

The main focus of this study was to determine the extent of integration of Global Citizenship Education Competencies (GCED) relative to cognitive, socio-emotional and behavioral domains in the teaching of English in San Pascual District, Province of Batangas, Philippines. It also included the teachers' assessment on the importance of integrating the competencies. Moreover, it also sought to find out if there was significant relationship between the extent of integration and the assessment of teachers on importance of integrating the competencies. It also identified the topics in intermediate curriculum where GCED competencies can be integrated. Based on the result, the researchers prepared activities integrating global citizenship competencies. The study employed quantitative-qualitative-descriptive research design, with questionnaire as the main for data gathering as well as documentary analysis. The respondents of the study were the 57 intermediate English teachers. No sampling was used in determining the respondents. In analyzing the gathered data, statistical tools used were weighted mean, composite mean and correlation. Results revealed that the GCED competencies in the cognitive, socio-emotional and behavioral were integrated to a great extent in the teaching of English by the intermediate teachers. They also agreed that these competencies are important and must be consistently integrated to further enhance the global citizenship skills of the learners. Meanwhile, there are various topics in intermediate English curriculum where GCED competencies can be integrated across cognitive, socio-emotional and behavioral domain. The researchers prepared activities to further integrate the competencies in the teaching of English language among intermediate learners.

Keywords: education, global citizenship competencies (GCED), descriptive, Philippines